

Studies on Optical Activity and Chemical Constitution. Optically Active Acids and Bases. Part II.

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In a previous communication (Singh and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 219) it was shown that the introduction of the dimethylamino group in the *para* position raised the rotatory power of phenyliminocamphor to an enormous extent. We have now prepared *p*-diethylaminophenyliminocamphor and measured its rotatory constants in twelve solvents for three wave-lengths. These values (*vide* experimental) exceed those of the dimethyl compound. The order is, however, practically the same as that for the dimethyl compound in these solvents.

This compound was also examined in benzaldehyde solution and gave an extraordinary low value. It has $[\alpha]_D = 972^\circ$ which fell to $[\alpha]_D = 608^\circ$ after 27 hours.

The dimethyl compound described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and the diethyl compound are both phototropic and thermotropic. The change in colour of the dimethyl compound is so slight that it escaped notice in the first instance. The changes which these substances undergo are represented by the following schemes :—

pp'-Bisiminocamphordiphenylamine (Singh, Singh and Lal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1971) is phototropic as well as thermotropic, but in this case, the changes have been explained by assuming that the hydrogen atom of the amino group oscillates between the two carbonyl groups. This causes the conjugation in the molecule to become continuous and also explains its high rotatory power. In the dialkylaminophenyliminocamphors, however, there exists no possibility of this nature.

Iminocamphor and its aryl derivatives containing an azethenoid group are capable of existing in two stereoisomeric forms, *syn* and *anti*, though numerous derivatives of iminocamphor (Forster and others, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 944; Singh and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1919, 155, 944; 1920, 117, 980, 1599) exist in one form only (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2156; also Singh and Rai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 389). *p*-Dimethyl- and *p*-diethylphenyliminocamphors also show isomerism of this type, the two forms showing different rotatory powers.

The light orange variety of the dimethyl compound and the scarlet variety of the diethyl compound have higher rotatory powers than the corresponding yellow and light orange forms.

Solvent.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylphenyliminocamphor.	
	Light orange.	Yellow.
Benzene	2496°	2058°
Toluene	2396	1884
Aniline	3000	2896

The following are the values indicating a progressive change from one variety to the other.

<i>p</i> -Diethyl compound	in aniline $[\alpha]_D = 3322^\circ$	$\xrightarrow{2-3 \text{ hrs.}}$	3219°
		$\xrightarrow{6 \text{ hrs.}}$	3104°
		$\xrightarrow{2 \text{ days}}$	3000°
"	(Scarlet form) in ethyl alcohol $[\alpha]_D = 2982^\circ$	$\xrightarrow{2 \text{ hrs.}}$	
		$\xrightarrow{2 \text{ hrs.}}$	2763°
		$\xrightarrow{\text{exposed to sunlight}}$	2675°
"	(Light orange) in ethyl alcohol $[\alpha]_D = 2263^\circ$	$\xrightarrow{2 \text{ hrs.}}$	
		$\xrightarrow{\text{in dark}}$	2607.8°
		$\xrightarrow{\text{sunlight}}$	2306°
		$\xrightarrow{\text{sunlight}}$	2629°

It is, therefore, clear that an equilibrium mixture is obtained in the solution and in each case the final values approach one another. The substance could not be examined in other solvents as the quantity available was very small.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Diethylaminophenyliminocamphor.—Camphorquinone (1.82 g.) and *p*-aminodiethylaniline (1.64 g.) in absolute alcohol solution (25 c.c.) were refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The dialkylamines decomposed rapidly on exposure and

therefore a considerable amount of tarry matter was produced. The condensation product after cooling was poured into water. The tarry matter was removed after repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol, when it was obtained as light orange needles, melting at 102.5° , to a deep red coloured liquid, yield 10%. (Found: N, 9.18. $C_{20}H_{28}ON_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent).

It is readily soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol, benzene, carbon bisulphide, chloroform and other organic solvents. It dyes wool yellow and in alcoholic solution is an indicator analogous to methyl orange giving with mineral acids a pink and with alkalies a light yellow colour.

Specific rotatory powers of p-diethylaminophenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Conc.	Temp.	$[\alpha]_D$.	$[\alpha]_{5780}$.	$[\alpha]_{5461}$.
C_6H_6	0.0120 g./25 c.c.	32°	2292°	2667°	3271
$C_6H_5CH_3$	0.0123	33	2053	2419	3130
C_6H_5Cl	0.0122	32	2623	2848	3627
C_6H_5Br	0.0300	32	2667	2933	3667
$C_6H_5NO_2$	0.0122	33	2848	2869	3484
$C_6H_5NH_2$	0.0152	32	3322	3487	4770
"	0.0124	32	3104	3467	4596
"	0.0120	32	3000	3229	4166
C_6H_5CHO	0.0144	34	972		
	After 27 hours		608		
C_6H_5N	0.0135	33	2685	3000	3796
MeOH	0.0146	32	2603	2671	3562
EtOH	0.0120	32	2625	2750	3333
$(CH_3)_2CO$	0.0123	32	2276	2398	3232
$CHCl_3$	0.0120	32	2854	3021	3750
CS_2	0.0128	32	2441	2480	2952

The *p*-aminodiethylaniline used above was prepared by two methods, firstly by the reduction of *p*-nitrosodiethylaniline (*cf.* Cumming, Hopper and Wheeler, "Systematic Organic Chemistry," 1931, p. 387), secondly by the reduction of sodium salt of *p*-sulphobenzeneazodiethylaniline by stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. The yield in each case was 15-20%.

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